

The Consortium for
Biomedical Research &
AI in Neurodegeneration

C-brAIN: The Consortium for Biomedical Research and AI in Neurodegeneration
An Academic-Industry AI Consortium Accelerating Health-Impactful Discoveries in Brain Aging, Neuroscience, and Neurodegeneration

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Preamble

The Consortium for Biomedical Research and AI in Neurodegeneration (C-brAIN) White Paper introduces the AI Biomedical Research Scientist Initiative. An effort to revolutionize how biomedical research is conducted by harnessing the impressive capabilities of advanced artificial intelligence.

Three recent and critical developments in biomedical research form the basis for this initiative: 1) increasingly advanced AI technologies, 2) unprecedented volumes of actionable biomedical data, and 3) growing scientific expertise in how best to curate and train AI systems. The C-brAIN aims to unite these three developments to create an AI-driven Neurodegeneration Biomedical Research Scientist that deeply understands neurodegenerative diseases and is designed to work alongside human researchers.

This document serves as a strategic blueprint and an invitation for collaboration among academia, industry, philanthropy, and technology partners.

Figure 1: Core elements of the AI Biomedical Research Scientist. AI technologies, biomedical data, and expert scientists come together to create a collaborative, scientist-in-the-loop system.

Introduction

Neurodegenerative diseases remain among the most pressing challenges in medicine. They cause progressive decline in memory, cognition, independence, and ultimately death for millions of people worldwide and impose significant emotional, social, and economic burdens on patients, families, and healthcare systems. Despite decades of research and substantial financial investment, progress has been slow, and only a few moderately effective treatments currently exist.

More than 99% of drug candidates fail during clinical development in Alzheimer's disease, often because the underlying biological mechanisms are not fully understood or because trial designs cannot effectively identify the right patient populations [1,2]. Innovative solutions are essential to reduce the time, cost, and risk involved in developing effective treatments.

The problem is not a lack of scientific talent or dedication. The traditional method of scientific progress relies on long cycles of generating hypotheses, validating experiments, and interpreting results, a process that can stretch over years or decades. Data also remains fragmented in institutional silos, crucial insights are not integrated across disciplines, and negative results (a vital source of knowledge) are largely lost, making it extraordinarily difficult to make connections that could lead to breakthroughs. While individual researchers can and often do generate important discoveries, the field lacks integrated tools to systematically combine insights that could accelerate the pace of progress.

At the same time, we are witnessing an unprecedented explosion in biological data. Advances in molecular profiling, imaging, and electronic health records are generating new, vast, and diverse datasets. More than two million biomedical papers are published each year, with thousands focused specifically on neurodegeneration and Alzheimer's disease. Progress is often limited by the need to review and comprehend these vast amounts of biomedical information. The sheer breadth and depth of this expanding knowledge base is lengthening the time it takes to train new scientists, who must now master an increasingly wide array of methods and data types to contribute meaningfully to cutting-edge research. This paradox, possessing more data than ever yet struggling to extract actionable insights, has created a crisis of synthesis in biomedical research.

We believe it is possible to turn this challenge into an opportunity with the aid of advanced AI systems that can now intelligently understand data, design experiments, and interpret the biology of the human brain. The C-brAI envisions an AI Biomedical Research Scientist, a collaborative, scientist-in-the-loop system that helps researchers synthesize massive volumes of literature and data, generate new hypotheses, design experiments, and interpret results. Rather than replacing scientists, this AI system is intended to augment their capabilities and transform how research is conducted.

Vision for the AI Biomedical Research Scientist:

Mission:

To design and implement AI as a collaborative partner for scientists, accelerating discovery in neurodegeneration research to improve human health.

Vision:

We aspire to create AI systems that support and enhance human scientist expertise, accelerating breakthroughs and improve patient outcomes.

Unlike narrow AI tools built for single tasks, the AI Biomedical Research Scientist is conceived as a holistic platform consisting of multiple AI capabilities, each designed to assist at different stages of the scientific workflow: from reading and synthesizing literature to integrating diverse datasets, generating hypotheses, designing experiments, and interpreting complex results. From the earliest stages of basic research to the translation of discoveries into clinical applications, this system is intended to function less as a research tool and more as a true scientific collaborator. What makes this vision achievable is the convergence of advanced AI technologies capable of engaging meaningfully with the complexity of biomedical research. Recent breakthroughs include large language models (LLMs) that analyze scientific literature; knowledge graphs that map complex biological relationships; retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), which integrates information retrieval with generative AI to produce context-specific insights; multimodal data integration unifying diverse biomedical datasets; agentic systems capable of reasoning under human guidance; and federated learning, which enables machine learning across distributed datasets while preserving privacy. These core technologies are further strengthened by methods such as explainable AI, or XAI (for transparent decision-making), causal inference and counterfactual reasoning

(to uncover mechanistic insights), and reinforcement learning with human feedback (which allows AI systems to adapt and collaborate dynamically). Meanwhile, advances in computational power and modern software architectures also now make it possible to manage the scale and complexity of biomedical data. Together, these innovations form the technical foundation for developing an AI Biomedical Research Scientist.

Our vision establishes the scientist-in-the-loop approach not just as a principle, but as a core strategic advantage. We do not believe AI can or should replace scientists but rather enhance and expand their capabilities. In our approach, human scientific expertise will guide every stage of the process, validating AI-generated insights, refining hypotheses, and ensuring scientific rigor. Expert researchers will directly engage with the AI system by annotating outputs, providing feedback, and participating in structured refinement cycles. A dedicated Expert Feedback Portal will allow domain scientists to correct hypotheses, label errors, and refine the AI's reasoning through multiple feedback rounds. This partnership preserves trust, prevents black-box decision making, and ensures that AI remains focused on solving real problems in the context of biomedical science. The continuous involvement of biomedical research experts enables the AI to adapt to new discoveries, align with domain norms, and mirror expert scientific reasoning.

Our initiative is especially well-positioned to achieve this vision because it is ***built by scientists, for scientists***, bringing together proprietary data, deep neurodegenerative expertise, and a collaborative model that spans academia, industry, technology partners, and philanthropy.

Achieving this vision requires both immediate action and a clear path for long-term transformation. That's why the C-brAIN has structured its work as an intentional, phased process. In Phase 1, we are focused on delivering three targeted Minimum Viable Products (MVPs) that demonstrate the feasibility and value of AI tools in biomedical research. These MVPs serve as a gateway for Phase 2, which will involve integrating individual capabilities into a unified AI Biomedical Research Scientist, which will be a collaborative partner capable of supporting the full research cycle, generating cross-disciplinary insights, and extending its purview beyond Alzheimer's disease into broader biomedical challenges.

Figure 2: Phased development of the AI Biomedical Research Scientist. Phase 1 builds targeted Minimal Viable Products (MVPs) to demonstrate feasibility. These components feed into Phase 2, which integrates them into a unified, multi-domain AI system with a scientist-in-the-loop design.

Value for Diverse Stakeholders

- *Patients & Families*: Gain from accelerated discovery of effective diagnostics and treatments.
- *Pharmaceutical & Biotech Companies*: Enhance R&D pipelines with AI-augmented hypothesis generation, and failure de-risking.
- *AI Technology Partners*: Advance state-of-the-art technologies in multi-modal reasoning and human-aligned systems.
- *Biomedical Scientists & Clinicians*: Accelerate literature synthesis, design stronger, more impactful experiments; and explore diverse and broadly informed hypotheses.
- *Trainees (PhDs, MD/PhDs, Postdocs)*: Accelerate learning, insight generation, and mentoring via AI co-researchers.

The AI Biomedical Research Scientist is not an abstract idea for the distant future. It is an achievable goal being pursued today. We believe this system has the potential to transform the pace and impact of research in neurodegenerative diseases by shortening hypothesis-testing cycles, revealing connections across diverse datasets, and generating insights beyond what researchers or labs could produce alone. The C-brAI invites partners across all sectors to join us in building this vision for the future of scientific research.

Illustrative Use Case: Dr. Anya Sharma and the Scientist-in-the-Loop AI:

To help readers envision how the AI Biomedical Research Scientist might function in practice, we present one illustrative use case. While this scenario is fictional, it reflects the kind of capabilities the system aims to support. Many other variations are possible across disciplines, data types, and stages of the research pipeline.

Meet Dr. Anya Sharma, a postdoctoral researcher studying tau pathology. Her morning routine has been transformed. Instead of spending weeks manually searching PubMed and sifting through siloed datasets, she poses a query to the C-brAI platform: 'What are the emerging, under-investigated molecular pathways that connect lysosomal dysfunction to tau propagation, and are there any contradictions between the published literature and our consortium's unpublished preclinical data?' Within minutes, the AI Biomedical Research Scientist synthesizes thousands of relevant papers, cross-references them with proprietary datasets from three pharmaceutical partners, and flags a critical contradiction between a published finding and a negative result from a partner's discontinued trial. The system then presents Dr. Sharma with three novel, testable hypotheses, each complete with a preliminary experimental design, a ranked list of potential chemical probes, and traceable citations back to the specific public and private data sources that informed its reasoning.

The Foundations of Our Vision

The following sections describe the foundational technology, data, and expertise that position the C-brAI to succeed.

Technology

Recent advances in artificial intelligence and computational methods have fundamentally expanded the frontiers of biomedical research. These breakthroughs are powered by high-performance computing resources, such as GPU clusters and distributed computing environments, that make it feasible to train large-scale AI models and analyze complex, multimodal biomedical data.

Today, LLMs can read and synthesize vast bodies of scientific literature, revealing relationships and generating hypotheses across millions of publications. Ontology-driven natural language understanding further enhances this process by linking textual concepts to standardized vocabularies and structured databases, enabling researchers to connect literature insights to structured biomedical data and knowledge graphs. These graphs provide structured representations of biological systems, helping to uncover elusive connections among genes, pathways, clinical phenotypes, and outcomes that might otherwise remain hidden. Retrieval-augmented generation architectures, including advanced methods for graph-based retrieval, integrate information retrieval with generative AI to produce context-specific insights grounded in both published literature and proprietary data. In addition, emerging information extraction methods are beginning to capture structured data (such as tables, figures, and supplementary datasets) from scientific publications, enhancing the ability to integrate both narrative insights and underlying data. Meanwhile, multimodal data integration methods bring together diverse biomedical information (including omics, imaging, and clinical records) while federated learning enables machine learning across distributed datasets without the need for centralized data pooling, thereby preserving data privacy. Agentic systems enable goal directed activity with multiple cycles and systems to interact in complex ways.

In parallel, a complementary set of AI methodologies (such as explainable AI, causal inference, counterfactual reasoning, reinforcement learning with human feedback, and probabilistic modeling) has matured to enhance the utility and reliability of these systems. Rather than serving as standalone technical features, these methods work in concert to support transparent reasoning, adaptive learning, and robust inference under uncertainty. Collectively, they can enable AI systems to interact dynamically with human scientists, helping to refine hypotheses, interpret complex findings, and ensure scientific trustworthiness.

Together, these technologies have matured to a point where they can handle the scale, complexity, and sensitivity of biomedical data, providing the technical backbone for building AI systems that actively collaborate with scientists rather than serving merely as passive analytical tools.

Data

Over the past decade, neurodegenerative research (and biomedical science more broadly) has generated an unprecedented volume and diversity of data. These resources encompass genetics, transcriptomics, proteomics, imaging, cognitive assessments, clinical records, behavioral measures, and digital biomarkers. They include both well-established longitudinal cohorts and emerging real-world datasets, spanning human studies as well as data from animal models, which provide crucial mechanistic insights into disease biology.

Many of these datasets are vast, comprising terabytes or even petabytes of information collected across multiple time points, modalities, and populations. High-quality, curated resources such as DIAN, DIAN-TU, ACTC, ADNI, NACC, AIBL, EPAD, BioFINDER, Delcode, MCSA, ADSP, NIAGADS, GNPC or the AD Knowledge Portal provide rich, multimodal datasets specific to neurodegenerative diseases. Beyond these disease-focused resources, broader population cohorts like the UK Biobank, BSLA, the All of Us Research Program, FinnGen and Dutch 100+ contribute diverse genomic, imaging, and clinical data from large, heterogeneous populations.

Specialized datasets further enrich this landscape. Imaging-focused resources such as the Human Connectome Project and CAMCAN offer high-resolution brain imaging data, while digital biomarker studies like mPower and RADAR-AD provide novel, sensor-based measures of disease progression. Real-world clinical data sources (including TriNetX, Optum Clinformatics, and disease-specific registries) also offer valuable insights into patient populations and treatment patterns across routine clinical care.

Importantly, the C-brAI itself represents a growing network of partners (including academic research laboratories, pharmaceutical companies, and other stakeholders) each contributing unique and often underutilized datasets. These contributions span curated and uncurated data generated through specialized experiments, disease models, clinical trials, and observational studies, including negative data from experiments or trials that did not confirm initial hypotheses, which are essential for reducing bias and improving model accuracy. The consortium is also partnering with curated expert platforms such as AlzForum, which offers over 25 years of Alzheimer's-related commentary, peer-reviewed news, and structured biomedical databases [3]. Recognizing the scientific value of both empirical datasets and structured expert commentary, the consortium views these contributions as essential for helping the AI Biomedical Research Scientist learn not just what works, but also what does not. In particular, AlzForum's vetted discussions, community reviews, and longitudinal insights offer rich training signals that model how real scientists critique evidence, refine hypotheses, and reach consensus. This structured content will be integrated into knowledge graphs, summary evaluators, and hypothesis generators, by providing the AI with both factual grounding and a deeper understanding of scientific reasoning. Taken together, these investigator- and industry-generated datasets and expert knowledge platforms complement larger,

publicly available resources and add depth and diversity to the consortium’s data ecosystem. These and other examples are summarized in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Examples of Multimodal Data Resources Relevant to the C-brAIIn’s Vision (This list is not exhaustive). DIAN – Dominantly Inherited Alzheimer Network, DIAN-TU – DIAN Trials Unit, ACTC – Alzheimer’s Clinical Trials Consortium, A4 - Anti-Amyloid Treatment in Asymptomatic Alzheimer’s, LEARN - Longitudinal Evaluation of Amyloid Risk and Neurodegeneration, APEX – Alzheimer’s Plasma Extension Study, ADNI – Alzheimer’s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative, MCSA – Mayo Clinic Study of Aging, NACC – National Alzheimer’s Coordinating Center, AIBL – Australian Imaging, Biomarkers and Lifestyle Study, EPAD – European Prevention of Alzheimer’s Dementia, BioFINDER – Biomarkers For Identifying Neurodegenerative Disorders Early and Reliably, DELCODE – Deutsches Zentrum für Neurodegenerative Erkrankungen Longitudinal Cognitive Impairment and Dementia Study, ADSP – Alzheimer’s Disease Sequencing Project, NIAGADS – National Institute on Aging Genetics of Alzheimer’s Disease Data Storage Site, GNPC – Genomic Nexus for the Proteogenomic Characterization of Alzheimer’s Disease, AMP-AD – Accelerating Medicines Partnership – Alzheimer’s Disease, ROSMAP – Religious Orders Study and Rush Memory and Aging Project, BLSA – Baltimore Longitudinal Study of Aging, CAMCAN – Cambridge Centre for Ageing and Neuroscience, mPower – Mobile Parkinson Disease Study, RADAR-AD – Remote Assessment of Disease And Relapse – Alzheimer’s Disease.

Dataset/Resource	Type of Data	Description / Relevance
Alzheimer’s-Specific, Curated Datasets		
DIAN-TU, ACTC (A4/LEARN, AHEAD-3-45/APEX)	Multimodal, longitudinal	Deep genetic, imaging, cognitive, and biomarker data from interventional trials in familial and preclinical Alzheimer’s disease.
DIAN, ADNI, MCSA, NACC, AIBL, EPAD, BioFINDER, Delcode	Multimodal, longitudinal	Imaging, CSF/biomarkers, cognitive assessments, and sequencing data across diverse Alzheimer’s cohorts.
ADSP, NIAGADS, GNPC, AD Knowledge Portal (AMP-AD, ROSMAP, etc.)	Multi-omics	Genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, metabolomic, and clinical data from AD patients and controls
General Population and Aging Cohorts		
UK Biobank	Genomics, imaging, clinical	Large-scale data integrating genetic profiles, imaging, and health records from over 500,000 participants.
BLSA	Clinical, imaging, genomics	Longitudinal cohort tracking physiological and cognitive aging with deep clinical, imaging, and genomic profiling.
All of Us Research Program	Genomics, clinical, digital health	U.S.-based, diverse cohort data including EHRs, surveys, and wearable device data.
FinnGen	Genomics, clinical	Finnish cohort linking genetic data to national health records for disease insights.
Dutch 100+	Genomics, phenotyping	Deeply phenotyped centenarian cohort for understanding resilience and healthy aging.
Specialized Neuroscience / Digital Biomarker Studies		
Human Connectome Project, CAMCAN	Neuroimaging, cognitive	High-resolution brain imaging and behavioral data for understanding brain networks.
mPower, RADAR-AD	Digital biomarkers	Mobile/wearable sensor data capturing daily activity and disease progression signals in neurodegeneration.
Real-World datasets		
TriNetX, Optum Clinformatics	Real-world data, EHRs	Federated EHR networks, claims data, clinical datasets
Private, Investigator-Contributed, and Curated Knowledge Resources		

Proprietary Pharma Data	Clinical trials, real-world, preclinical	Unpublished trial data, negative results, observational studies critical for new hypothesis generation.
Individual Research Labs	Experimental, multi-modal	Investigator-held data from animal models, high-dimensional assays, and novel experiments—often unpublished.
AlzForum	Curated literature, structured knowledge	Alzheimer’s-focused commentary, peer-reviewed news, curated databases, and community consensus.

Recognizing that data interoperability is essential for multi-institutional research, the C-brAIN initiative will define and implement a strategy for data harmonization that balances standardization with flexibility. One potential approach involves mapping heterogeneous data sources to a Common Data Model (CDM), which can provide a standardized structure and vocabulary to enable unified querying across datasets. For instance, the consortium may explore adapting widely used models like the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) CDM with neurodegeneration-specific extensions. Regardless of the model ultimately adopted, the harmonization strategy will emphasize transparency, quality control, and metadata integrity to support scientific rigor and reproducibility.

At present, this extraordinary data landscape remains fragmented across institutions, research groups, and industry partners. Much of it cannot be centralized due to privacy considerations, proprietary interests, or regulatory constraints. To address this, the C-brAIN will pursue federated learning and privacy-preserving data architectures, enabling AI systems to learn from distributed datasets without requiring raw data to be pooled in a single location. This approach preserves data sovereignty while still allowing the AI Biomedical Research Scientist to extract insights from diverse sources. Equally important, the consortium is committed to fostering an environment of trust and shared purpose, where researchers and partners are motivated to contribute data because they see clear scientific value, opportunities for collaboration and innovation, and meaningful recognition for their contributions. Partners who join the C-brAIN gain the opportunity to uncover new insights from integrated analyses, discover unexpected connections across diverse datasets, and become part of a pioneering community committed to accelerating breakthroughs in neurodegenerative disease research.

Expertise

Even with powerful technologies and rich data resources, the AI Biomedical Research Scientist requires one more essential ingredient to be successful: human scientific expertise. The C-brAIN is founded on the principle of the human-in-the-loop. In this case, scientist-in-the-loop training and implementation. We believe that scientists remain indispensable to the research process and can ensure that AI outputs are scientifically rigorous, clinically relevant, and ethically sound. Domain experts in neurodegenerative diseases bring deep knowledge of biological pathways, clinical manifestations, and therapeutic challenges, while data scientists and AI engineers contribute the technical skills to design scalable and interpretable computational systems tailored to biomedical problems. Just as important are pharmaceutical researchers who understand the realities of drug development, regulatory requirements, and the complex pathways through which discoveries are translated into patient care. This diverse community (including collaborators from academia, industry, technology companies, government and philanthropy) ensures that the AI Biomedical Research Scientist will be shaped by experts who understand both scientific challenges and patient needs.

Our Phased Approach

While the C-brAIN's long-term goal is to transform biomedical research across many diseases, we have chosen Alzheimer's disease and neurodegenerative disorders as our initial focus. This provides both an urgent area of unmet need and a rich landscape of available data and expertise to build and test the AI Biomedical Research Scientist. Our phased approach is designed to culminate with a unified AI Biomedical Research Scientist capable of accelerating discovery across multiple disease areas.

Phase 1: Minimum Viable Products Under Development

The C-brAIN initial efforts center on developing targeted MVPs that deliver immediate, practical value to researchers and stakeholders, while demonstrating the real-world feasibility of the AI Biomedical Research Scientist.

MVP 1: AI Literature and Data Synthesis

The first MVP focuses on AI Literature and Data Synthesis, aiming to help researchers quickly extract and synthesize the most important scientific findings across the rapidly expanding neurodegenerative disease literature. Unlike conventional tools that merely search or summarize text, this MVP generates accurate results by combining LLMs with advanced techniques such as Graph-based Retrieval-Augmented Generation (e.g. GraphRAG, lightRAG), enabling it to connect insights across publications, identify relationships among key concepts, and surface emerging hypotheses relevant to specific research questions. In addition to textual synthesis, this tool is designed to parse structured data embedded within scientific publications (such as tables, figures, and supplementary datasets) further enriching the insights provided to researchers. By integrating literature analysis with semantic reasoning and initial steps toward data interrogation, this MVP will empower scientists to navigate complex biomedical knowledge faster and more effectively than existing solutions.

Stakeholder impact: This capability will benefit any researcher through faster, accurate literature synthesis, biotech and pharma scientists seeking to integrate proprietary and public data, and technology partners interested in advanced scientific search tools.

MVP 2: Negative Data Analyzer

The second MVP addresses a significant blind spot in biomedical research: the vast amount of negative or null-result data that goes unpublished or unnoticed despite scientists recognizing these negative results as critical to avoiding redundancy, refining hypotheses, and ensuring efficient scientific progress [4]. This tool will ingest and analyze negative data (whether from publications, internal studies, or unpublished datasets from pharmaceutical and academic sources) to help researchers avoid repeating failed experiments, identify hidden insights, and better understand the conditions under which hypotheses may or may not hold true. Unlocking the value of negative data can reduce wasted effort and reveal new avenues for exploration.

Stakeholder impact: Negative Data Analyzer empowers pharma R&D, translational scientists, and academic researchers.

MVP 3: Reviewer Three

The third MVP is envisioned as a virtual reviewer that provides critical feedback on experimental designs, hypotheses, data interpretation and critical evaluation of manuscripts. Drawing upon existing literature, best practices, statistical and ethico-legal considerations, this tool aims to function as a knowledgeable, rigorous scientific peer, helping researchers refine their proposals and reduce avoidable errors. Unlike static checklists or generic writing assistants, Reviewer Three draws upon scientific reasoning and domain-specific knowledge to emulate an experienced reviewer's critical perspective.

Stakeholder impact: Reviewer Three facilitates grant writing, improves experimental designs, or conducts critical reviews of findings to assist researchers and research teams.

Collectively, these MVPs are not endpoints but steppingstones toward Phase 2, where the consortium aims to integrate these capabilities into a cohesive AI Biomedical Research Scientist. Each MVP serves as a proof-of-concept, validating core technical approaches, engaging end users, and demonstrating tangible benefits. Insights gained from MVP 1 can inform the critique generated by Reviewer Three, while patterns surfaced by the Negative Data Analyzer may guide new literature searches and hypothesis generation. They also create essential building blocks (such as data pipelines, user interfaces, and knowledge graph architectures) that will form the backbone of the comprehensive AI Biomedical Research Scientist.

The Expert Feedback Portal: Operationalizing the Scientist-in-the-Loop Model

The C-brAI scientist-in-the-loop framework relies on structured human-AI interactions to improve model performance. A central opportunity is the collection of explicit feedback, where researchers deliberately evaluate, annotate, or correct the AI's outputs. To support this, the initiative will incorporate an Expert Feedback Portal, a digital interface modeled on pharmaceutical "lab-in-the-loop" automation pipelines [5]. Such a portal could enable domain experts to provide feedback in a consistent, structured format suitable for fine-tuning of the AI's reasoning through reinforcement learning from human judgment. Example features of an expert feedback portal for collecting explicit feedback could include:

- **Hypothesis Triage Dashboard:** Domain experts rate AI-generated hypotheses on novelty, feasibility, and impact, producing immediate, quantifiable signals of value.
- **Interactive Evidence Annotation:** Users upvote or downvote individual evidence sources, correct misinterpretations, and add missing contextual information.
- **Structured Error Flagging:** A standardized interface allows experts to tag specific problems (factual inaccuracies, logical fallacies, unsafe suggestions), using a shared taxonomy, that feeds back into the model's fine-tuning process.
- **Confidence Calibration:** The AI would present its own confidence estimate alongside expert ratings; mismatches between the two generate direct error signals, teaching the system to better estimate its uncertainty ("knowing what it doesn't know")[5].

In parallel with explicit interaction, implicit feedback may also be derived from routine expert behaviors within the research environment. For example, patterns in how users select hypotheses for further analysis, ignore certain outputs, or repeatedly revise particular suggestions could provide rich, latent signals of scientific value. These indirect cues might be extracted and aggregated over time to adjust the AI's internal reward functions and help prioritize outputs that align more closely with expert decision-making.

Together, explicit and implicit feedback mechanisms support scientific rigor in the present while laying the groundwork for future development. By capturing scientist critique, annotation, and calibration data, the system generates a high-quality training corpus that supports the development of more advanced AI reasoning capabilities. These scientist-in-the-loop interactions are not a peripheral feature; they serve as the scaffolding for Phase 2. As development progresses from targeted MVPs to a unified, multi-domain AI Biomedical Research Scientist, this feedback infrastructure becomes capable of training foundation models that reason with human-like nuance across literature, data, and experimental design.

Phase 2: Building the Unified AI System

Phase 2 envisions an AI Biomedical Research Scientist that acts as a true collaborative partner to human researchers. Unlike isolated tools built for single tasks, this unified system will work to connect literature synthesis, data integration, hypothesis generation, experimental design, and results interpretation into one coherent platform[6–9].

In Phase 2 we will develop foundational AI models trained directly on raw biomedical data. Unlike tools that merely summarize existing literature, these models will learn to understand biological context, recognize complex patterns in diverse data types, discern mechanisms, and generate novel hypotheses grounded in scientific evidence. Recognizing that no single AI architecture can excel across all types of biomedical information, the consortium will adopt a modality-aware approach combining the most effective technologies. For example, transformers for text and literature, state-space models for genomic and time-series data, graph neural networks for biological relationships, and specialized vision models for imaging. By tailoring models to each data modality’s unique structure and scale, we aim to unlock insights that remain hidden to general-purpose AI systems and build a platform capable of translating vast biomedical data into actionable scientific discoveries.

The scientist-in-the-loop principle remains central in Phase 2. To uphold this standard, we will adopt open, community-driven benchmarking frameworks, akin to the DREAM Challenges [10], which enable transparent evaluation and invite broad participation from academia and industry. By embedding these benchmarks into Phase 2, we aim to instill confidence that our models are scientifically robust, reproducible, and capable of delivering real-world impact.

Equally essential to Phase 2 is our commitment to scientific reproducibility and data privacy. We will build this AI Biomedical Research Scientist on transparent, shareable foundations, so that data pipelines, models, and analyses are documented, open-sourced where possible, and designed for independent verification. This approach will hopefully enable other researchers to build upon our work, accelerating progress across the scientific community. At the same time, we recognize the sensitivity of biomedical data and the regulatory requirements that protect it. To address this, we will incorporate privacy-preserving methods (such as federated learning and advanced techniques like synthetic data generation or secure multiparty computation) yielding collaborative insights without compromising confidentiality. These principles will ensure our system remains scientifically rigorous, trustworthy, and compliant with the highest standards of biomedical research.

As the platform matures, Phase 2 is designed to expand beyond Alzheimer’s disease into other complex biomedical challenges. The foundational models, knowledge graphs, and analytical pipelines developed in earlier phases will provide a scalable architecture, enabling the system to adapt efficiently to new disease areas. By leveraging a modality-aware approach, the same platform can integrate diverse data types—whether genomic data, imaging analyses for pathology, or wearable sensor data for monitoring chronic diseases. Critically, Phase 2 will also incorporate patient-centered data streams, such as digital biomarkers and real-world activity measures, to connect molecular insights with clinical outcomes and everyday experiences. This multi-domain capability will help the AI Biomedical Research Scientist accelerate discoveries across diseases and delivers insights that are meaningful and actionable for patients and researchers alike.

Phase 2 will extend the AI Biomedical Research Scientist from discovery into clinical translation, focusing on both preventive and therapeutic applications. By analyzing data across the continuum from healthy individuals to those showing early disease signs, the system aims to identify risk factors and early indicators that could inform prevention strategies. Simultaneously, it will help accelerate therapeutic development by suggesting potential drug targets, refining patient cohorts for clinical trials, and uncovering insights from multi-modal treatment data.

Through Phase 2, the C-brAIIn aims to develop an AI tool that can accelerate discoveries and improve patient care. The anticipated impacts of this unified system are described in the next section.

Impact and Measures of Success

To ensure transparency and accountability, we are defining metrics and indicators of success. These will help us track progress, adapt our strategies, and demonstrate tangible value to our partners and stakeholders.

Metrics associated with MVP delivery:

- **Number and diversity of public and proprietary datasets integrated:** Demonstrates our efforts to build a comprehensive data ecosystem that fuels new discoveries for academic researchers and helps pharma partners validate findings across datasets.
- **On-time completion and integration of platform modules:** Confirms steady progress toward delivering key MVP components (such as literature synthesis tools, negative data analyzers, and virtual review modules) and offering novel capabilities for scientific discovery research.
- **System performance benchmarks:** Ensures tools are fast, accurate, and reliable, measured by benchmarks such as response time, retrieval precision and recall, exact match rates, and alignment with expert-reviewed biomedical answers.

Engagement metrics:

- **Number of active users and research projects engaging with the platform:** Reflects both widespread interest and real-world integration into scientific workflows, ensuring tools are used meaningfully rather than explored in isolation.
- **Frequency and type of tool usage:** Shows how researchers and partners are incorporating AI tools into daily workflows, which should reduce bottlenecks in literature review, data analysis, and experimental planning.
- **Diversity of participating institutions and publications citing consortium tools:** Reflects broad buy-in across academia, industry, and technology, fostering collaboration and shared knowledge.
- **Usability assessment:** Directly measure how the tools are being used to meet scientists' needs, guiding future improvements to ensure real-world usability.

Impact metrics:

- **Reduction in time for literature review and data integration:** Measured by tracking time from initial research queries to completed analyses, papers, or grant proposals, allowing researchers to focus more on creative, hypothesis-driven science.
- **Contributions to experimental design and grant proposals:** Measured by improvements in study design quality, clarity of scientific hypotheses, experimental reproducibility, and positive feedback from peer reviewers or funders, increasing the likelihood of successful research outcomes and funding.
- **Identification of previously unknown insights across data types:** Measured by expert evaluations of novelty and relevance, and by tracking how AI-generated insights lead to new experiments, publications, patents, or other evidence of scientific impact.
- **Avoidance of redundant experiments and improved trial design:** Provides pharmaceutical partners with critical intelligence to de-risk development pipelines, reducing costs and accelerating timelines.
- **Integration of negative data insights:** Helps the entire research ecosystem avoid known pitfalls, improving the efficiency and effectiveness of future studies.

The goals of these metrics are to substantially improve the mission of the consortium: to accelerate biomedical research discoveries that lead to positive human health impact.

Success Metrics & Development Timeline

Quantifiable impact will be assessed through:

- Time-to-hypothesis: Reduction by $\geq 50\%$ compared to manual review methods.
- Experimental success: $\geq 2\times$ improvement in reproducible, validated findings
- Discovery throughput: $\geq 3\times$ increase in AI-assisted insights leading to publications or patents.
- Generalization: Demonstrated applicability to ≥ 2 non-Alzheimer's biomedical domains by year 3
- Researcher engagement: ≥ 100 labs interacting with platform within 24 months.

Timeline:

- **Year 1:** MVP validation and user testing across 3 partner labs
- **Year 2:** Unified model integration with cross-site federated deployment
- **Year 3:** Expansion to other diseases; semi-automated hypothesis-experiment workflows

Architecting a Resilient Consortium

The C-brAI is committed to ensuring that the AI Biomedical Research Scientist becomes a resource that benefits the entire biomedical research community, and ultimately, patients worldwide.

We believe that openness is a practical necessity for achieving real scientific impact. Sharing tools, methods, and knowledge enables discoveries in one lab or institution to spark insights and advancements in others. It fosters broader validation of new approaches, encourages faster adoption of innovative technologies, and supports more consistent scientific standards. For stakeholders across the ecosystem, this translates into tangible benefits: academic scientists gain new tools and insights; pharmaceutical partners can access collaborative innovations that help de-risk development; technology providers can integrate advanced capabilities into their platforms; and patients ultimately benefit from faster translation of research into diagnostics and treatments.

Central to realizing this vision is the consortium itself. Through C-brAI, diverse stakeholders can come together to create, test, refine, and share resources. This model allows us to combine world-class scientific expertise, advanced AI technologies, and unique data assets (including proprietary and unpublished datasets from industry partners) within a secure, ethical, and coordinated framework.

Our commitment to openness and collaboration takes many practical forms. We intend to:

- Release tools and methods under licenses that encourage broad use and adaptation.
- Publish findings and methodologies in open-access journals and platforms.
- Engage researchers and partners through workshops, training programs, and pilot collaborations.
- Work closely with funders and industry partners to ensure global accessibility and equitable impact.

However, we also recognize that successful collaboration requires more than open sharing. It also demands clear standards, governance, and trust. To that end, the consortium is developing guidelines and structures to confirm that all shared tools and resources are implemented responsibly and ethically, and that privacy, data integrity, and scientific rigor are upheld.

Delivering the Vision: Roadmap and Operational Framework

This initiative launches on July 30, 2025, marking the beginning of coordinated efforts to deliver measurable results and tangible impact.

Phases and Milestones:

- **July 2025:** Consortium launch.
- **Year 1 (Phase 1):** Development and pilot testing of three MVPs: AI Literature and Data Synthesis, Negative Data Analyzer, and Reviewer Three.
- **Years 2–3 (Phase 2):** Integration of MVP capabilities into a unified AI Biomedical Research Scientist platform using an Expert Feedback Portal. Design and training of foundation models on multimodal biomedical data. Expansion into disease areas beyond Alzheimer’s.
- **Beyond Year 3:** Deployment of a unified system capable of accelerating discoveries, supporting drug development, and improving patient outcomes across multiple biomedical domains.

Governance and Operational Framework

To ensure transparency and accountability, the C-brAI will operate as an independent entity governed through a balanced, multi-stakeholder approach. Its structure will include a Steering Committee, composed of representatives from academia, industry, technology, and philanthropy, that is tasked with setting strategic direction and ensuring diverse perspectives guide key decisions. An independent executive body will oversee day-to-day management and coordination, while specialized working groups will focus on essential areas such as technology architecture, data standards, bioethics, responsible AI, and legal frameworks.

Governance Body	Composition	Mandate and Key Responsibilities
Steering Committee	Representatives from each partner category (Academia, Industry, Tech, Philanthropy, Patient Advocacy).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sets overall strategic vision and approves annual budget. • Approves new consortium partners. • Final dispute resolution.
Executive Body	Full-time Consortium Director, Program Managers, and staff.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manages day-to-day operations and tracks milestones. • Facilitates communication between all partners and working groups.
Working Groups	Technical, legal, and ethical leads from partner organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology & Architecture WG: Oversees platform design and technical standards. • Data Governance & IP WG: Manages the IP policy and oversees a Data Access Committee (DAC). • Ethics & Responsible AI WG: Develops and oversees the ethical framework and dual-use risk mitigation.
External Advisory Board	Independent, internationally recognized experts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides objective, external review of scientific progress and strategic direction.

Partner Benefits and Value Proposition

We recognize that contributing valuable data and expertise requires a compelling incentive beyond altruism. Our "give/get" model ensures a tangible return on investment for our partners. Contributing partners will receive contractually defined benefits, which may include priority access to integrated insights and seats on key governance and scientific committees. We welcome partners to engage at every stage, contributing data, expertise, or pilot collaborations that help transform this vision into reality.

Framework for Privacy and Responsible AI

Federated learning is a key pillar of the C-brAIN privacy strategy, but it is not a complete solution. Even model updates can unintentionally leak sensitive information. To address this, a multi-layered approach is under consideration, one that combines technical safeguards with administrative oversight to protect data and support compliance with regulations such as HIPAA and GDPR. Illustrative strategies to support privacy could include:

- **Federated Data Architecture:** Raw data remains within the data owner's secure environment and is never centralized.
- **Differential Privacy:** Statistical noise is added to model updates to provide mathematical guarantees against the re-identification of individual data points.
- **Secure Aggregation:** Cryptographic methods enable aggregation of model updates without decrypting individual contributions.
- **Administrative Oversight:** A formal Data Access Committee (DAC) could review and approve analysis proposals, governed by enforceable Data Use Agreements (DUAs).

In parallel, C-brAIN would establish an Ethics and Responsible AI Working Group to explore issues such as the potential misuse of therapeutic discovery tools, flagging of high-risk queries, and ethical review of potentially hazardous applications. This group could also address sustainability and ensure compliance with environmental standards.

Call to Action

The C-brAIN firmly believes that the AI Biomedical Research Scientist can transform biomedical discovery and bring faster, more impactful breakthroughs to patients worldwide. We also believe we have the technology, the data, and the expertise, but we still need more collaboration to make this vision a reality.

As such, we invite **academic researchers** to join pilot projects, contribute domain expertise, and help shape tools for literature synthesis, hypothesis generation, experimental design, and data interpretation to ensure these systems remain scientifically rigorous and practical for real-world research. By collaborating, researchers gain access to advanced platforms that can integrate knowledge and support more efficient, innovative studies.

We welcome **pharmaceutical and biotechnology partners** to explore how these AI capabilities can accelerate target discovery, improve trial design, and enhance translational research. Securely integrating proprietary data (including negative results and past trial outcomes) can unlock new insights, reduce redundancy, and improve success rates across the field. By partnering, pharmaceutical and biotech organizations can potentially uncover insights that de-risk R&D pipelines and unlock value from proprietary data.

We seek **technology collaborators** ready to integrate advanced AI methods into this scientific ecosystem. Expertise in AI, data engineering, and scalable infrastructure will help turn ambitious ideas into practical, trusted solutions. Working with the consortium offers a unique opportunity to apply cutting-edge technology to critical biomedical challenges.

We also encourage **philanthropic funders** to help scale these efforts, support open-source development, and ensure equitable global access to AI-driven research tools. Philanthropic support can help build a foundation that benefits countless research groups and accelerates progress for patients worldwide.

Across all partners, the C-brAI offers opportunities to:

- Join working groups focused on scientific and technical challenges.
- Participate in pilot projects to test and refine AI tools.
- Contribute unique datasets or insights to accelerate discovery.
- Help shape the initiative's priorities and future directions.
- Support dissemination and training to ensure widespread adoption.

New AI tools provide a critical opportunity to reshape how biomedical research is conducted and bring hope to millions waiting for tomorrow's discoveries. But making it happen will require vision, collaboration, openness, and the expertise of humans across a variety of fields, disciplines, and sectors. We hope and expect the C-brAI can bring people together to take advantage of this exciting technology to bring relief to families suffering from Alzheimer's Disease and other neurodegenerative conditions.

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